

THE CONCEPT AND GENESIS OF "IMAGES" IN ARTISTIC LITERATURE

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8081270>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 16th June 2023

Accepted: 25th June 2023

Online: 26th June 2023

KEY WORDS

Image, artistic image, imagery, fiction, perception, reflection, literary studies, Aristotle, Hegel, V.G. Belinsky, artistic vision, imagination, existence.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the concept of artistic "image", its development, its entry into fiction, the concepts of "artistic image", "imagery".

The concept of image is so important in fiction that it is impossible to imagine a work of art without images. Because in literature, the vision of life is expressed through artistic images. The first ideas about the image were put forward by Aristotle, and it was understood to describe a certain reality in literature and art by means of images. In the 19th century, this concept was further clarified by Hegel and V. G. Belinsky. Hegel, who brought this definition to science for the first time, explained the figurativeness of literature as follows: "We can define a poetic image as a figurative image, because it replaces its abstract essence before our eyes with its specific reality"¹.

While defining the concept of image in literary studies, a number of our scholars have given different definitions:

I.Khotamov, B.Sarimsakov "Literary terms in the Russian-Uzbek dictionary" Landscapes and characters that reflect life in a unique artistic form in art and literature. The image is the reflection of the objective reality in one way or another in the human mind"². Any situation, incident, situation that happens around us first of all draws its expression, its reflection, its line in our mind. This, in turn, causes the same events to be transferred to the image, to be sealed in the image. The term "image" is taken from the Russian language and means "mirror" in Uzbek translation. For example, a person's reflection in a mirror is said to be "image". However, you know that there is a difference between the lexical meaning of the word and the idiomatic meaning: although there are points of contact between the lexical meaning and the idiomatic meaning, the specialist's understanding of the concrete meaning under the term is it

¹ Гегель. Эстетика. Т. 4. М., 1958. — 194.

² I.Xotamov, B.Sarimsoqov "Adabiyotshunoslik terminlarining ruscha-o'zbekcha izohlilug'ati. T.: "O'qituvchi", 1979. 200-b

will be necessary. Accordingly, by "image" we mean an artistic image, a form of thinking in literature and art"³.

"An artistic image is a reflection of existence (thing, event, etc.) in an artistic work. However, an artistic image is not a simple reflection of that being, no, it is a reflection of the being seen by an artist's eye and creatively processed on the basis of an ideal. In this image you will find many familiar traces of existence, but it is no longer the same existence as we know it, but a completely new existence - an artistic existence"⁴. An artistic image is the total existence that surrounds us, the events that we repeatedly worked on, aesthetically enriched, and creatively recreated through our imagination. All the events that the human mind can reach and fit into the world of imagination find their expression in images. As noted by literary scholar D. Kuronov, "the image subject of literature is, first of all, a person. There is no image of a person, and there is no fiction where it is not provided"⁵. Any image of reality that has been creatively processed through the human mind and clearly manifested its abstract reflection in literature and art is considered. Any word that we understand with our mind can be seen through images. When we hear the concept of "Mother" in our minds and imaginations, when we see in front of our eyes a beautiful woman who is the dearest of all in the world, the kindest of all, who gave her life only for us, when we say "Motherland", our child who was playing, the most beautiful thing in our whole life. Our house, the witness of our happy moments, the bright reflection of our neighborhood before our eyes is considered an artistic image.

Artistic image is used in literary studies in a broad and narrow sense. In a narrow sense, we can only understand a person, and in a broad sense, as literature and art reflect the whole being, an object, object, event-event in the artistic representation of reality is considered an image. Since the main subject of literature is man, all events serve only and only for man in the process of artistic creation. In this process, the concept of "imagery" shows its importance. So, in an artistic work, we creatively describe a certain event, object, human character, it is considered an artistic image. In fiction, in the work of art, the supreme being, the supreme creature, is depicted in close connection with the human being, the whole being, society and its processes, the surrounding nature, socio-spiritual environment, things and phenomena. . Because human beings are always surrounded by them. However, all of these serve to show the uniqueness of the human image, or to emphasize that it has similar aspects to others, or to give emotional impact to the human image, that is, to fill one of its aspects. They show their strength as auxiliary tools. The highest goal and intention of an artistic image is often the person himself. The image of things and events does not have an independent artistic value by itself, they are needed to show a person more brightly, to reveal his nature more deeply. But man cannot exist alone. A person needs a lot of things to live like a person and show his humanity. In fiction, along with the person, the image of the environment is also necessary. Only their image in fiction is subordinated to the human condition and experiences. The writer reflects reality and interprets it as he understands it. Only after the events in life, people and their worldview, character trait, cultural-scientific level, intention, and desire are

³ Dilmurod Quronov. Adabiyotshunoslikka kirish. ziyouz.com kutubxonasi. 68-b

⁴ Д.Куронов, З.Мамажонов, М.Шералиева. Адабиётшунослик луғати. Т.: «Академнашр». 2013. 43 б

⁵ Д.Куронов, З.Мамажонов, М.Шералиева. Адабиётшунослик луғати. Т.: «Академнашр». 2013. 45 б

processed, the image appears in the form of symbols and takes the form of a work of art. In short, the writer in the creative process individualizes and summarizes the images in his work. Depicting a person means, first of all, describing his inner world and experiences. A person lives among people, that is, in society. Human experiences are closely related to various social issues. Therefore, fiction should reflect the human experience in all its complexities. This requires high talent and artistic skill from the creator. He should know life and people well, reflect the situation of a person, as much as possible, truthfully, as he feels with his heart. Only then can his works have a strong impact on people's hearts, arouse joy, educate people in the spirit of faith in goodness and love for beauty. So, in fiction, a picture of a person created in the form of a separate person, which at the same time has the characteristics of artistic generalization and the power of emotional impact, is called an artistic image"⁶.

Fiction is based on the idea of beauty. Such an imagination was born from the dreams of a person about a person, life and society. A work of art will have educational power only if it reflects these dreams. In the image, objective perception and subjective creative thinking are mixed. The specific characteristics of the artistic image are clearly manifested in the relationship to reality and the thinking process. The image, as an artistic reflection of reality, has the emotionally clear, materially complete, mature characteristics of a real existing object, lasting in a certain time and space. The artistry of the image is not determined by the ability to reflect and understand the existing reality, but the artistry appears in the ability of the image to create an unprecedented, newly conceived world. Along with the objective and important aspects of the image, the possible, the goal, the desire, that is, the attitude to the emotional and volitional aspects of life, and the features related to its invisible, internal possibilities are also sealed. Also, a work of art is created by creatively using imagination, paint, sound, words, etc. in an artistic image.

It can be seen that, based on the above, in art and fiction, we are created by the imagination and talent of the word artist, indirectly and transformed, to convey the image of reality, using verbal means and words. We can see a re-created vision of a changed imaginary world through the medium of an artistic image.

A picture of human life depicted in a visual-artistic literature, a work of art, the writer describes life and expresses his thoughts about it, using images to reveal the attitude of people to the behavior of people in different conditions, to natural phenomena, and by showing them in the work, he expresses his thoughts. does. An artistic image is a form of reflection of reality by art, a clear and at the same time generalized image of human life, modified on the basis of the aesthetic ideal of the artist, created with the help of creative imagination. An artistic image can be a part of a work of art, but it can also be equal to, or even surpass, a work of art. Artistic image is one of the most important terms of art and literary studies, it serves to show the connection between reality and art, and it most clearly expresses the specific characteristics of art in general. An artistic image is usually defined as a form or means of reflecting reality in art, its characteristic feature is the expression of an abstract idea

⁶ Д.Куронов, З.Мамажонов, М.Шералиева. Адабиётшунослик луғати. Т.: «Akademnashr». 2013. 43 б

in a concrete emotional form. An artistic image is a category of aesthetics that describes a special way of mastering and transforming reality inherent in art. Image is also called any phenomenon that is creatively recreated in a work of art. Each of them contributes to the development of this concept, and their analysis allows to identify general rules of interest for this study.

It should be taken into account that the image is not a logical concept and is created not on the basis of scientific-theoretical thinking, but on the basis of generalized subject imaginations, moods, experiences, and is a form of assimilation of the phenomena of the external and internal world of human existence in artistic works. An artistic image not only reflects and understands the existing reality, but also creates a new, imaginary world, creatively transformed by the author of a literary work. This creation of imagination is based on the material collected in the life experience of the writer. Fiction becomes a way of generalization, an attempt to give general characteristics to individual facts, and this is achieved on the basis of the writer's or poet's rich life experience. Fiction creates a clear picture of a person's life, through which generalization begins to shine and inevitably leads the reader to evaluate this or that life event.

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